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THE TEACHER-STUDENT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IMAM AL-BUKHARI AND
IMAM AT-TIRMIDHI

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the great contributions to Islamic science and the teacher-student relationship between two great stars of Islamic science, Imam Al-Bukhari and his student At-Tirmidhi.*

The scholar Imam al-Bukhari also paid great attention to the study of knowledge and put forward the following ideas in his works: "A person cannot become a qualified hadith scholar unless he learns hadith not only from his superiors or peers in knowledge, but also from those who are inferior to him." With this idea, Imam Bukhari emphasizes the formation of a positive motivation for educational activities by the teacher.

Key words: *Khadith, spiritual heritage, Islam, religion, muhaddith, "Al-Jame' as-Sahih", "Sahih al-Bukhari".*

Аннотация. *В этой статье обсуждается большой вклад в исламскую науку и отношения учителя и ученика между двумя великими звездами исламской науки — Имам Аль-Бухари и его учеником Ат-Тирмизи.*

Энциклопедист Имам аль-Бухари также выдвигает в своих произведениях следующие идеи: «Человек не может стать зрелым мухаддисом до тех пор, пока не получит хадисы не только от своих начальников или сверстников, но и от тех, кто ниже его». Имам Бухари подчеркивает, что положительные мотивы учебной деятельности формируются учителем.

Ключевые слова: *Хадис, духовное наследие, ислам, религия, мухаддис, «Аль-Джаме ас-Сахих», «Сахих аль-Бухари».*

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada islom ilm-fanining ikki buyuk yulduzi Imom Al-Buxoriy hamda uning shogirdi At-Termiziylarning islom ilm-fanidagi ulkan hissalarini va ustoz shogirdlik munosabatlari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Qomusiy olim Imom al-Buxoriy ham ilm o'rganishni yuqori darajaga qo'yib, o'z asarlarida quyidagi fikrlarni ilgari suradilar: «Kishi ilm bobida nafaqat o'zidan yuqori yoki tengdoshlaridan, balki o'zidan past bo'lganlardan hadis olmaguncha, yetuk muhaddis bo'la olmaydi». Imom Buxoriy ushbu fikri bilan o'quv faoliyatining ijobiy motivlari ustoz-muallim tomonidan shakllantirilishiga urg'u beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Hadis, ma'naviy me'ros, islom dini, muhaddis, "Al-Jomi' as-Sahih", "Sahih al-Buxoriy".

Introduction. Imam Bukhari and Imam Tirmidhi are considered great hadith scholars who occupied important places in Islamic history. Their teacher-student relationship played a very important role in the development of Islamic science.

Imam al-Bukhari was born on July 20th, 810, in Bukhara. Imam Bukhari's father died when he was young, and he was raised by his mother. From a young age, he was intelligent, sharp-witted, and had a strong desire for knowledge, and he studied various sciences, especially the science of hadith, with great interest. In 825, sixteen-year-old Bukhari traveled to the Hijaz with his mother and older brother Ahmad to perform the Hajj pilgrimage. He visited the holy cities of Mecca and Medina, lived in the Hijaz for 6 years, and then lived in cities such as Cairo, Basra, Kufa, and Baghdad, which were considered major centers of learning at that time, in order to further his knowledge of the science of hadith.

Imam al-Bukhari's most famous work is undoubtedly "Al-Jame' as-Sahih." The four-volume collection of hadiths entitled "Al-Jame' as-Sahih" is the most reliable and complete of any collection compiled by other hadith scholars in the Islamic world. This book is also known as "Sahih al-Bukhari", and its most important feature is that Imam al-Bukhari divided the hadiths he heard from different narrators into categories, separated the reliable ones, and created a separate book.

The hadiths included in Imam Bukhari's collections do not merely reflect the general principles of Islamic teachings. They are a collection of true human virtues and exemplary practices, such as love, generosity, respect for parents and elders, kindness to orphans, compassion for the poor and needy, love for the homeland, hard work and a call to honesty.

One of the great scholars who created globally significant works on hadith is the famous hadith scholar Abu Isa Muhammad at-Tirmidhi. Due to the sharpness of Tirmidhi's mind, memory, and ability to memorize, Imam al-Bukhari respected him not only as a student, but also as a colleague and friend.

Known as an accomplished scholar of hadith of his time, Al-Tirmidhi taught many students. Among his students in the science of hadith are Muhammad ibn Mahmud Anbar, Hamad ibn Shakir, Ahmad ibn Yusuf Nasafi and others.

The most famous of Imam Tirmidhi's works is undoubtedly "Al-Jami'", which is considered one of the six authentic collections of hadith. This work is also referred to in literature and sources as "Al-Jami' as-Sahih", "Jami' at-Tirmidhi", "Sunan at-Tirmidhi".

The hadiths recorded by At-Tirmidhi, like the hadiths narrated by Imam al-Bukhari, are important in teaching people the ideals of honesty, justice, purity, hard work, compassion, and respect for elders and children.

Master-Discipleship Relationship:

- Influence of Imam Bukhari: Imam Tirmidhi was a disciple of Bukhari and was shaped by the scientific and moral influence of his teacher. Bukhari's book "Al-Jami' as-Sahih" had a great influence on Tirmidhi, and he used Bukhari's style in writing his book "Al-Jami' as-Sahih".

- Spreading knowledge: Imam Tirmidhi developed the knowledge of his teacher and ensured its wide dissemination. He also took Bukhari's teachings to other countries during his scientific travels.

Imam Tirmidhi had great respect for his teacher Bukhari. He always mentioned in his books that he used Bukhari's advice and teachings. Bukhari also highly valued his student Tirmidhi. He recognized Tirmidhi's scientific abilities and accepted him among his students.

Conclusion.

The mentor-disciple relationship between Imam Bukhari and Imam Tirmidhi played an important role in the development of Islamic scholarship. Both Imam Al-Bukhari and Imam At-Tirmidhi made essential contributions to the study and development of Islam. Their methods of collecting, critically analyzing, and classifying hadith served as models for later generations of scholars. Bukhari's influence shaped Tirmidhi's scholarly work, while Tirmidhi helped disseminate Bukhari's knowledge. Their mutual respect and collaboration contributed greatly to the development of Islamic religion and culture. Their books continue to play a significant role in the lives of Muslims today, strengthening their faith and shaping their moral education.

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